

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**AN OVERVIEW – FORMULATION AND ASSESSMENT OF
MULTIPURPOSE FACE CREAM****Ms. Saranya V¹, Ms. Shilpa B S¹, Ms. Swathy Krishna¹, Mrs. Aparna P², Mrs. Jebitha J R³, Dr. Prasobh G R⁴**¹B. Pharm Students, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India²Associate Professor, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India³Assistant Professor, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India⁴Principal, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India**Abstract:**

A cosmetic product is defined as any substance or preparations intended to be placed in contact with the various external part of human body. Cosmetics are the preparations used to beautify and enhancing the human appearances. The face cream is prepared by using the turmeric powder, neem powder and carrot oil. The aim of this study was to prepare a multipurpose face cream for the purpose of brightening, antibacterial property and treating tan. The choice of ingredients is based on the various medicinal properties of these agents. The cream is tested on different evaluation parameters. Turmeric powder is used as an anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial agent. Neem powder acts as a natural antiseptic, antibacterial and antifungal agent.

Key words: Cosmetics, face cream, turmeric powder, neem powder, carrot oil

Corresponding author:**Saranya V, Shilpa B S, Swathy Krishna**

B.Pharm students,

Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala,
Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, IndiaEmail: vijayansaranya27@gmail.com, shilpabs01122001@gmail.com,
swathykrishnamani@gmail.com**QR CODE**

Please cite this article in press Saranya V et al., An Overview – Formulation And Assessment Of Multipurpose Face Cream, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(11).

INTRODUCTION:

The definition of cosmetic under the law varies slightly between countries but in general terms "cosmetic" means any article intended to be used by means of rubbing, sprinkling or by similar application to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, altering the appearance of the human body and for maintaining health of the skin and hair, provided that the action of the article on the human body is mild.¹

The word "cosmetic" shares its roots with the word "cosmos," which is derived from the Greek word "kosmos," which means "order" or "ornament." The word "cosmetic," which refers to the outward look, has come to have a second connotation. They concentrate on maintaining the 'appearance' of the external body surfaces, such as the skin, hair, and teeth, as well as deodorizing or perfuming them to eliminate odors. Changing the appearance of these surfaces, safeguarding them and maintaining their integrity or as in the other sense of "kosmos" keeping them in good "order" are also included in definitions.²

CATEGORIES OF COSMETICS

Cosmetics may be categorized according to the body part over which they are applied. All cosmetics are typically intended to be applied externally to the face (on the skin, lips, eyebrows, and eyes), to the body (on the skin, in particular the hands and nails), and to the hair. The cosmetics have been categorized into,

1. Cosmetics for Hair
2. Cosmetics for Nails
3. Decoration of Dental care
4. Cosmetics for Skin

HAIR COSMETICS

Hair cosmetics are an important tool that helps to increase patient's adherence to alopecia and scalp treatments. This article reviews the formulations and the mode of action of hair cosmetics: Shampoos, conditioners, hair straightening products, hair dyes and henna; regarding their prescription and safety. The dermatologist's knowledge of hair care products, their use, and their possible side effects can extend to an understanding of cosmetic resources and help dermatologists to better treat hair and scalp conditions according to the diversity of hair types and ethnicity.³

NAIL COSMETICS

Nail cosmetics industry is growing at an enormous rate globally due to a surge in nail care all around the world. Various nail cosmetics are available, such as nail polish along with its variants like shellacs, finishes, artificial nails, adornments, and

nail polish removers. Nail cosmetics serve aesthetic as well as therapeutic purposes, with the end result being smooth, attractive nails. Nail grooming procedures have evolved from a basic manicure to many other advanced procedures like gel nails, nail tattooing, etc. Although a majority of nail cosmetics are considered safe, they may have potential complications, including allergic and irritant reactions, infections, and mechanical effects. The majority of the procedures related to nail enhancement are not performed by dermatologists but by beauticians with inadequate or no knowledge of the nail's anatomy and functions. The hygiene at the so-called nail-salons/beauty parlours is not standardised, leading to acute complications like paronychia and nail dystrophy following matrix injury. The use of nail cosmetics has become widespread, making it essential for dermatologists to be aware of the nail care products, aesthetic procedures pertaining to nails, and related adverse effects.⁴

DENTAL CARE COSMETICS

Modern day dentistry is much more advanced as it focuses both on the pain, discomfort as well as the increasing demand of the youths towards fashion and trends. To stand out different and do something "out of the box" this generation has found different aesthetic ways to make their smile shinier and recognizable. This article discusses about such fashionable trends both invasive and non-invasive and also about their complications. Some of these are present since many years and are practiced on large scale around the globe. Some are said to have cultural values and some were performed as a rite of ownership. Non-invasive techniques involve tooth gems, twinkles/studs, tooth tattoos, tooth rings and dental grills whereas invasive procedures involve oral piercing in which there are tongue piercing, tongue splitting, lip and cheek piercing and lip surgical procedures in which there are lip repositioning, lip reduction and lip augmentation. In non-invasive technique no soft tissue is involved and there is no blood loss either. On the other hand invasive one involves soft tissue and there is loss of blood also. Many advanced techniques and materials are developed over the decades to reduce complications but some of the complications are very difficult to reduce. Though these are thought to add more bling to the smile, there is nothing as beautiful as natural. As it is said by Ashokha-"Natural beauty remains longer than artificial settings." But as a millennial generation we are also more attracted and fascinated by such things.⁵

SKIN COSMETICS

Cosmetics are applied on skin to enhance the personality, beauty, colour, complexity, tone, texture etc. Maintaining a healthy skin is important

for a healthy body. Skin is a protective covering and an attractive feature of the body for both men and women. It forms an important part of personal appearance. There are various cosmetic preparations available in the market like creams, lotions, oils, soaps, gels, moisturizers, etc. These cosmetics can be applied on the skin to enhance beauty and protect the skin from different skin disorders like acne, blackheads, age spots, skin rashes, skin allergy etc. There are also other preparations which include antiageing creams, skin whitening agents, gels etc. for protecting the skin from UV radiations, sunscreen lotions and moisturizing creams to protect the skin from different climatic conditions. In the present scenario most of the cosmetics products are adulterated. There are various other cosmetic preparations in the market which are of spurious quality which may produce some side effects like skin rashes, skin allergic reactions and may lead to skin diseases. In this paper we have reviewed different medicinal plants used as cosmetics and these preparations can be used safely without side effects on the skin. In this article a special emphasis has been given to herbal cosmetics because herbals are a part of our life and their uses are increasing day by day all over the world. Scientists are still working on the evaluation of new methods that could increase our knowledge and enable to find new applications for it.

ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF SKIN

The skin is the largest organ in the body, covering its entire external surface. The skin has 3 layers—the epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis, which have different anatomical structures and functions. The skin's structure comprises an intricate network that serves as the body's initial barrier against pathogens, ultraviolet (UV) light, chemicals, and mechanical injury. This organ also regulates temperature and the amount of water released into the environment.

Skin thickness varies by body region and is influenced by the thickness of the epidermal and dermal layers. Hairless skin in the palms of the hands and soles of the feet is the thickest due to the presence of the stratum lucidum, an extra layer in the epidermis. Regions lacking this extra layer are considered thin skin. Of these regions, the back has the thickest skin because it has a thick epidermis. The skin's barrier function makes it susceptible to various inflammatory and infectious conditions. In addition, wound healing, sensory changes, and cosmesis are significant surgical concerns. Understanding the skin's anatomy and function is crucial for managing conditions across all medical fields.

Figure 1: Anatomy of skin

EPIDERMIS

Epidermis is the most superficial layer of skin and is composed of stratified epithelium. From the deepest to the most superficial, the epidermal layers are the stratum basale, stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum, stratum lucidum, and stratum corneum.

DERMIS

The dermis is connected to the epidermis by the basement membrane. The dermis consists of 2 connective tissue layers, papillary and reticular, which merge without clear demarcation. The papillary layer is the upper dermal layer, which is thinner and composed of loose connective tissue that contacts the epidermis. The reticular layer is the deeper layer, which is thicker and less cellular. This layer consists of dense connective tissue composed of collagen fibre bundles. The dermis houses the sweat glands, hair, hair follicles, muscles, sensory neurons, and blood vessels.

HYPODERMIS

The hypodermis, also known as the subcutaneous fascia, is located beneath the dermis. This layer is the deepest skin layer and contains adipose lobules, sensory neurons, blood vessels, and scanty skin appendages, such as hair follicles.⁶

FACE CREAM

A face cream is a semisolid cosmetic preparation applied to the skin of the face. It serves to moisture, nourish and protect the skin from external factors. Face creams are generally oil-in-water or water-in-oil emulsions. They maintain the natural moisture balance of the skin. The cream forms a thin film over the skin that prevents water loss through evaporation. It provides smoothness and softness to the epidermal layer. Face creams can be classified into day creams, night creams and medicated creams depending on use. A well-formulated face cream enhances the appearance and texture of the skin. It

acts as a protective barrier against dust, sunlight and pollutants. Face cream often contain vitamins, antioxidants and herbal extracts for extra benefits. They are used as a base for makeup and other cosmetic products. The formulation may include humectants, emollients and occlusives to retain moisture. Emulsifiers and stabilizers help to maintain uniform consistency. Preservatives are added to prevent microbial contamination. Fragrance and coloring agent are incorporated for aesthetic appeal. Modern formulations often include sunscreens and anti-aging ingredients. The Ph of a good face cream is usually close to that of skin. The texture should be non-greasy and easily spreadable. A face cream should be safe, stable and non-irritant for all skin types. Overall, face cream plays a vital in maintaining healthy, youthful and radiant skin.

Figure 2: face cream

ADVANTAGE:

- Keeps the skin hydrated and soft.
- Protects the skin from dryness, wind and pollution.
- Improves skin tone and elasticity.
- Serves as an excellent base for cosmetics.
- Provides nutrients and antioxidants to the skin.

DISADVANTAGE

- Some creams may cause allergic reactions due to fragrance or preservatives.
- Overuse can lead to clogged pores and acne.
- May become unstable under extreme temperatures.
- Short shelf life if not properly preserved.
- Some formulations may leave a greasy residue on the skin.⁷

TURMERIC POWDER

Botanical source: *Curcuma longa* linn Family: Zingiberaceae

Chemical constituents: Curcuminoids, Volatile oils (turmerone, atlantone, zingiberene) Therapeutic

uses:

- Used as an anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial agent
- Promotes wound healing and skin health
- Aids digestion and supports liver function
- Traditionally used for treating cough, cold and joint pain
- Widely used as a natural coloring agent in food and cosmetics⁸

Figure 3: Turmeric

NEEM POWDER

Botanical source: *Azadirachta indica*

Family: Meliaceae

Chemical constituents: Azadirachtin, Nimbin, Nimbidin, Nimboesterol, Gedunin, Salannin, Quercetin

Therapeutic uses:

- Acts as a natural antiseptic, antibacterial and antifungal agent.
- Used in the treatment of acne, eczema and other skin infections.
- Promotes wound healing and reduces inflammation.
- Possesses insecticidal and antiparasitic properties.
- Commonly used in herbal cosmetics, tooth powders and hair care formulations⁹

Figure 4: Neem Powder

CARROT OIL**Botanical source:** *Daucus carota***Family:** Apiaceae

Many vegetable plants can be used as medicinal plants, one of which is carrot (*Daucus carota* L.). Carrot is a vegetable plant that has many uses for public health services in the world. Besides being rich in nutritional content, especially vitamin A and high antioxidants, it is also efficacious for healing various diseases as well as smoothing the skin and for beauty¹⁰.

Figure 5: Carrot Oil**VARIOUS CHEMICAL USED****Table 1: Role of ingredients**

SL. NO	INGREDIENTS	ROLES
1	White beeswax	Base, thickening agent
2	Stearic acid	Stiffening agent, texture enhancer
3	Liquid paraffin	Oil base, emollient
4	Aloe vera gel	Moisturizing agent, soothing agent
5	Neem powder	Antimicrobial agent
6	Turmeric powder	Antioxidant, antiinflammatory agent
7	Carrot oil	Antioxidant
8	Lavender oil	Fragrance
9	Methylparaben	Preservative

METHOD OF PREPARATION:

The face cream was prepared by using ingredients beeswax, stearic acid, liquid paraffin, turmeric powder, neem powder, aloe vera gel, carrot oil, and lavender oil by the fusion method. It involves melting all waxy and oily ingredients together at a controlled temperature (around 70 °C), incorporating active ingredients, and allowing the mixture to cool under continuous stirring. This produces a homogeneous semi-solid cream.

FORMULATION OF MULTIPURPOSE FACE CREAM

Weigh beeswax, stearic acid, and liquid paraffin accurately. Place them in a clean china dish and heat to 70°C on a water bath until all waxy components are completely melted. Stir continuously to obtain a uniform, clear solution. To the melted oil phase, add turmeric powder, neem powder, aloe vera gel, carrot oil, and lavender oil slowly with continuous stirring. Maintain the temperature around 70°C during addition to ensure proper dispersion of powders and uniform mixing. Continue stirring constantly until all ingredients are evenly mixed. If using trituration method, to avoid air entrapment. Remove the china dish from heat and allow the mixture to cool gradually to about 40°C with gentle stirring. This promotes proper solidification and smooth texture formation. Once semi-solid consistency is obtained, transfer the

cream into clean, dry containers or jars. Label properly and store in a cool, dry place¹¹.

EVALUATION OF MULTIPURPOSE FACECREAM**1. Organoleptic Evaluation:**

The organoleptic evaluation involves assessing the physical appearance, color, odor, and texture of the cream¹².

2. Spreadability:

Spreadability determines how easily the cream can be applied to the skin surface. It is evaluated by placing a fixed quantity of the cream between two glass slides and applying a 100gm weight for a specific time. The ease and uniformity with which the cream spreads indicate its consistency and suitability for topical application. An ideal cream should spread smoothly with minimal effort, ensuring even application¹³

$$\text{Spreadability} = m \times l/t$$

Where,

m = weight on the upper side l= length of glass side

t= time taken in minutes

3. Phase Separation:

The phase separation test is conducted to check the

stability of the emulsion system with in the cream. Samples are stored at various temperatures (4°C, 25°C and 40°C) for several days and observed for any signs of oil and water layer separation. A stable cream should not exhibit any phase separation or creaming under normal or accelerated storage conditions, ensuring uniformity throughout its shelf life¹⁴

4. Dye Test:

The dye test helps determine the type of emulsion used in the cream a small portion of the cream is mixed with a water-soluble dye such as amaranth red and examined under a microscope. If the continues phase appears coloured, the cream is identified as an oil in water emulsion, which is typically more suitable for facial use as it is lighter and easily washable¹⁵.

5. Washability Test:

Washability determines how easily the cream can be removed with water. A small amount of cream is applied to the skin and then washed with plain water or mild soap solution. A good face cream should be easily washable, leaving no greasy or sticky residue after cleaning. This characteristic is especially important for daily use cosmetics¹⁶

6. pH Determination:

The pH of the cream is a important parameter for ensuring skin compatibility. It is measured by dissolving one gram of cream in nine millilitres of distilled water and checking the pH using a calibrated digital pH meter. The pH ideally falls within the range of 5.0- 6.5 to match the natural pH of skin and prevent irritation or dryness¹⁷.

7. Stability Test:

The stability test is conducted to determine the physical and chemical stability of the cream under different environmental conditions. The formulation is stored at different temperature and humidity conditions (4°C, 25°C, 40°C, and 75% relative humidity) for up to three months. Observations are made for any changes in color, odor, consistency, pH, or phase separation. A stable formulation maintains its uniformity and properties throughout the testing period¹⁸.

8. Dilution Test:

The dilution test confirms the type of emulsion by mixing the cream with water. If the cream mixes readily with water, it is an oil – in – water (O/W) type; if it separates, it is a water- in – oil(W/O) type. Most face creams are formulated as O/W emulsions since they are light, easily spreadable, and washable¹⁵.

9. Homogeneity test

Ensures uniform mixing without lumps or phase separation¹⁹.

CONCLUSION:

Creams are semisolid formulation widely acceptable by the society. The purpose of face cream is to moisturize dry skin and cool the body

while also removing waste from pores. By using turmeric powder and neem powder shower anti-tanning with beautifying effect. Cosmeceutical has been extensively improved in personal care system and there is a great demand for cosmetics nowadays. Topical application of cream provides great photoprotective effect and could useful in human skin care. Creams can be modified with drugs and can be used with optimal delivery system for different skin diseases. The new approaches include incorporating bioactive ingredients with clinically proven therapeutic benefits into dermo cosmetics emollient.

The skin receives additional conservation from water phase with the use of face cream. The skin is the most accessible part of the body and as such is also highly vulnerable to injuries. Research and development for the formulation of pharmaceutical face cream for beautifying and makeup removal purpose has grown in recent decades owing to its obvious benefits. With the progress in the pharmaceutical field/ industry, it is assured that pharmaceutical face cream will still/ be an interesting and appealing area of research for years to come. More advanced technologies and methods will be used for preparation, formulation and evaluation of face creams in coming years.

REFERENCES:

1. Mitsui T, *Introduction of cosmetics*. Netherlands: Elsevier Science B.V.; 1997. P. 3–4.
2. Barton S, Eastham A, Isom A, Mclaverty D, Yi Ling Soong. *Discovering Cosmetic Science*. Royal Society of Chemistry; 2020.
3. Gavazzoni Dias MFR. Hair cosmetics: An overview. *International Journal of Trichology* [Internet]. 2015;7(1):2. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PM4387693/>
4. Tyagi M, Singal A. Nail cosmetics: What a dermatologist should know! *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology* [Internet]. 0(0):1–8. Available from: <https://ijdvl.com/nail-cosmetics-what-a-dermatologist-should-know/>
5. Singi SR, Sathe S, Reche AR, Sibal A, Mantri N. Extended Arm of Precision in Prosthodontics: Artificial Intelligence. *Cureus*. 2022 Nov 1;
6. Yousef H, Alhadj M, Fakoya AO, et al. Anatomy, skin (integument), epidermis [Internet]. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan– [updated 2024 Jun 8; cited 2025 Oct 4]

7. Barel AO, Paye M, Maibach HI. Handbook of Cosmetic Science and Technology. 5th ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2021.
8. Kaur, G., et al. Pharmacognosy of Curcuma longa. Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 2018, 7(3): 2193-2196
9. Subapriya, R., & Nagini, S. Medicinal properties of neem (Azadirachta indica): A review, Current Medicinal Chemistry – Anti-Cancer Agents, 2005,5(2): 149-156
10. Musnaini, Fransisca S, Leslie W. Effectiveness of cream formulation of carrot seed oil as anti-aging. Int J Health Pharm
11. Piyush B, Rushikesh B, Darshan S, Rutuja N, Ruchita B, Ganesh S and Dhananjay P, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Cream
12. Bhalekar MR, Pokharkar VB, Madgulkar AR. Formulation and evaluation of cosmetic herbal creams. Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res. 2017;45(2):45–50.
13. Mutimer MN, Riffkin C, Hill JA, et al. Spreadability of semisolid ointment bases: Method of measurement. J Am Pharm Assoc. 1956;45(3):212–218.
14. Martin A, Bustamante P, Chun AHC. Physical Pharmacy: Physical Chemical Principles in the Pharmaceutical Sciences. 4th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2002.
15. Aulton ME, Taylor KMG. Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines. 5th ed. London: Elsevier Health Sciences; 2013.
16. Shinde PR, More HN, Kadam VJ. Evaluation of cosmetic cream formulated from herbal extract. Int J Res Cosmet Sci. 2018;8(1):25–30.
17. Gupta GD, Garg R. Stability studies of cosmetic formulations. Indian J Pharm Sci. 2002;64(6):455–458.
18. Rawlins EA. Bentley's Textbook of Pharmaceutics. 8th ed. London: Baillière Tindall; 2008.
19. Kaur CD, Saraf S, International Journal of PharmTech Research. 2010;2(1): 63-70